

Study of Vibrational Motion Laws of Acetonitrile Molecule by Combination Scattering and Infrared Spectroscopy Methods

Allaquliyeva Shakhlo Hakimboy qizi¹, Otajonov Shavkat², Eshchanov Bakhodir Xudoyberganovich³

^{1,2}National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek
³Chirchik State Pedagogical University

Email: ¹shahloallquliyeva@gmail.com

Received 04/09/2023 **Accepted** 28/09/2023

Abstract

Using combination (Raman) and infrared spectroscopy methods, the regularities of interatomic hydrogen bonds in the acetonitrile molecule, which belongs to the methyl group of hydrocarbons, were studied in the frequency range of 0-3500 cm⁻¹. Based on the results of experiments and theoretical calculations, it was determined that the role of hydrogen bonds in the manifestation of combined light scattering and infrared absorption spectra is special. A number of parameters reflecting the laws of vibrational motion of the molecule associated with hydrogen bonds were theoretically calculated. A structural model of the acetonitrile molecule was created based on quantum-chemical calculations.

Keywords: spectroscopy, combination, spectrum, infrared, polarizability, relaxation, frequency.

1. INTRODUCTION

Studying the laws of vibrational spectra of molecules using combination scattering (CS) and infrared (IR) absorption spectra is one of the main methods for analyzing relaxation processes resulting from intermolecular interactions in liquids. Determining the micro and macro parameters of the relaxation processes with the help of these spectra provides the opportunity to obtain the necessary information about the structure of the medium.

Intermolecular interaction in liquids causes the atoms in the molecule to change their bond patterns. In particular, it can also lead to broadening of vibration spectra. If the lifetime of this process is relatively large, it causes a change in the frequency of the spectrum associated with the vibrational motion of the molecule. This time is significantly larger than the relaxation time of internal molecules vibration, and in liquids it does not exceed a few tens of picoseconds.

The regularities of CS and IR spectra are well studied in solid bodies, and there is also clear information about the mechanisms of manifestation of optical spectra. In particular, IR spectra were taken on a silicon dioxide film and the mechanisms of formation of optical spectra were analyzed [1]. The laws of hydrogen bonding in polyvinyl films were studied using the IR spectroscopy method [2]. CS spectrum was studied in lithium crystal with hydrogen compound, which can be used as an electricity source in hydrogen energy [3,4,5].

CS and IR spectra were also analyzed in liquid media in this area and relevant conclusions were drawn. Raman spectra of cyclic hydrocarbons and their halogen-substituted hydrocarbons were experimentally studied in the frequency range of 15-1500 cm^{-1} at a temperature of 295 K [6]. Results of research on the formation of molecular clusters of dimethylformamide and the studies dedicated to investigate molecular clusters of liquid dimethylformamide and its solutions are presented [7]. In the study of IR and Raman spectra of the species present in formaldehyde-water-methanol systems, it was studied that formaldehyde reacts with water and methanol to form various hydrated and methoxylated species. [8]. The possibility of qualitative and quantitative determination of asymmetric dimethylhydrazine, one of the important components of rocket fuels, by means of Raman spectroscopy with a laser with a radiation wavelength of 532 nm was considered [9]. The structure and shape of the spectra for vibrational CSOL spectra of ethanol molecules in toluene solutions were analyzed, and the possibilities of using them to obtain information about the characteristics of molecular interactions and their vibrational dynamics were shown [10]. C-O vibrations were studied for the methanol molecule [11], and information was obtained about the laws of aggregation of molecules. The combination light scattering spectrum of quinoline and its mixtures was studied, and two spectra were observed in the range of 1000-1040 cm^{-1} of the wave number, and its relation to the vibration of the quinoline molecule was studied [12]. Spectra formed by rotational-vibrational motion of atoms in organic substances containing methyl and halogen compounds in the benzene ring, which have symmetric and asymmetric properties according to the polarizability tensor, were studied by combinational and molecular light scattering methods [13-17].

Based on the analysis of scientific works published in this field, it should be noted that unlike solids, if we take into account the presence of strong intermolecular interaction forces in liquid substances, especially the properties of molecules with a complex structure and its structure has not been fully studied to date. The capabilities of existing molecular theories are also limited. Even the results of some scientific researches are sharply different from each other, and the mechanisms of manifestation of CS and IR spectra are approached differently.

Taking into account the above, it should be noted that the study of the nature of the intermolecular interaction forces in condensed matter and the regularities of the optical spectra of molecules with a complex structure is one of the most relevant fields of modern spectroscopy.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This scientific research work is dedicated to investigation of laws of formation of optical spectra associated with the vibrational motion of the acetonitrile – $\text{C}_2\text{H}_3\text{N}$ molecule using CS and IR absorption spectra. The arrangement structure of the atoms in the acetonitrile molecule, which is considered the object of the experiment, is represented in Fig. 1

Fig. 1. Chemical structural formula of the acetonitrile molecule

Special attention is paid to the cleanliness of the environment in spectroscopic research, and the composition of the research object must be free of other particles. The acetonitrile "pfa" (pure for analysis) used in the experiment was further purified by an existing chemical method, regardless of whether it was pure for the experiment [18]. Its purity was determined by the value of the refractive index measured by the refractometric method. The CS spectrum was taken on a InViaRaman spectrometer of Renishaw. Monochromatic laser radiation with a wavelength of 532 nm was used as a light source. The structure of this device is represented in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Flow diagram of the InViaRaman spectrometer

In the device: 1- self-emitting monochromatic light source with a wavelength of 532 nm (Cobolt CW 532nm DPSS laser RL532C100) and a power of 100 mW; 2- a mirror with a reflection coefficient as high as possible, which directs the laser radiation spreading along a straight line from the light source to the beam separating plate; 3- light separating plate; 4- a microscope lens; 5- sample; 6- a focusing lens that directs the light radiation scattered at an angle of 90° to the slit; 7- slit that transmits the light beam to the spectrometer; 8- spectrometer with a diffraction grating that performs the task of separating the scattering spectrum of scattered light; 9- CCD detector that provides the ability to obtain a graph of the frequency distribution of the intensity of the combinational scattering spectrum of light. InViaRaman spectrometer works in wavelength range from 200 nm to 2200 nm, its spectral resolution is 0.3 cm^{-1} , the number of lines per 1 mm of the diffraction grating is 1200 The IR absorption spectrum was obtained on a Spectrum Two FT-IR spectrometer (PerkinElmer). This spectrometer is able to record the absorption, transmission and reflected infrared spectra

of the medium, in the spectral range of $8300\text{-}350\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (for KBr optical part), and its ability to separate spectra is 0.5 cm^{-1} , the fully wavelength recovery is equal to $\pm 0.01\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

CS and IR spectroscopy methods are complementary to each other. If the polarization of the molecule changes under the influence of electromagnetic wave radiation, CS is active, and if the dipole moment of the molecule changes, IR is active. Vibrations of atomic bonds are observed in both spectra, but these spectra differ in intensity. Analyzing the pattern of vibrational spectra in polyatomic molecules is pretty complex. Because atoms participate in several vibrations at the same time. The movement of atoms inside the molecule is considered a complex process, and if the nonlinear molecule consists of N atoms, the number of vibrational degrees of freedom is equal to $3N-6$. The number of vibrational degrees of freedom is equal to the number of specific vibrations of the molecule. Each of these particular vibrations has its own particular frequency. Absorption occurs in a certain range of frequencies and forms IR spectra. According to the regularities of the IR spectra, the vibration of the molecule in the valence vibration causes a change the distance between the atoms to in the direction of the bond between the atoms. In deformation vibration, the distance between the atoms remains unchanged, which causes the angles between the atoms to change. Fig. 3 shows a general overview of CS in the $0\text{-}3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ frequency range and the IR absorption spectra in the $4000\text{-}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ frequency range for the acetonitrile molecule. The analysis of frequency distribution patterns of CS and IR spectra shows that the number of CS and IR spectra is different from each other, and the absolute values of their intensities are also different. As mentioned above, the intensity of the CS spectra is related to the change in the polarizability of the molecule, and in the IR spectra it is related to the change in the dipole moment of the molecule. Let us consider the spectral interval associated with the C–H vibration of the CS spectrum. 7 spectra associated with C–H vibration were observed for the acetonitrile molecule, their frequencies correspond to values of 378, 919, 1374, 2253, 2734, 2934, 2944, 3004 cm^{-1} . The CS spectra corresponding to lower frequencies (378, 919 cm^{-1}) are associated with the rotation-shaking behavior of acetonitrile. It is important to know the values of the potential barrier height of the molecule (the activation energy of the molecule) in order to obtain relevant information about the laws related to the vibrational behavior of the acetonitrile molecule and the mechanisms of the manifestation of the spectra. There are several ways to determine this energy, and it can be calculated using the semi-empirical method [19,20]. Basically, it can be considered that the height of the potential barrier is equal to the energy difference created due to the repulsion of the molecules in mutual vibration. This energy is proportional to the energy of the C–H bond, and knowing its value, a number of microscopic parameters related to the hydrogen bond were calculated.

Fig. 3. CS and IR spectra associated with the vibrational motion of the acetonitrile molecule: a-CS, b- absorption IR

In particular, based on the application of Y.I. Frenkel's theory [21], the mean lifetime of H-bond was theoretically calculated from the equation $\tau = \tau_0 \exp(U/kT)$. Here $\tau_0 = \frac{1}{2\pi\nu c}$ and it is the time characterizing the vibration frequency of the molecule, ν is the vibration frequency of the molecule (the frequency corresponding to the maximum value of the intensity corresponding to the CS spectrum in Fig. 3). The vibrational time of the molecule and the H-bond lifetimes for different frequencies of the CS spectrum related to the acetonitrile molecule are given in Figures 4, 5.

Fig. 4. Dependence of the vibrational time on the vibrational frequency for the acetonitrile molecule

Fig. 5. Dependence of the H -bond mean lifetime on the vibrational frequency for the acetonitrile molecule

The analysis of the regularity noted in Figure 5 shows that the mean lifetime of the C-H hydrogen bond of the acetonitrile molecule decreases with the increase in the vibration frequency of the molecule, which corresponds to the maximum values of the CS spectrum intensity observed in the experiment. In particular, it decreased from $1,58 \cdot 10^{-14}$ s to $0,19 \cdot 10^{-14}$ s. The CS and IR spectra in Fig. 3 show that the frequencies of the valence vibrations related to the C - H bond in the acetonitrile molecule are different from each other. For

example, the spectrum corresponding to the value of 1374 cm^{-1} of the frequency in the CS spectrum is equal to 1375.57 cm^{-1} in the IR spectrum and there is a shift by 1.57 cm^{-1} . Since this difference in CS and IR spectra is small, it can be concluded that C-H vibrations has a homogeneous and stable regularity. The intensities of the spectra are sharply different from each other, and the intensity of the IR spectrum is several times greater than that of the CS spectrum. Therefore, the IR spectrum is active and associated with a change in the dipole moment of the molecule. Quantum-chemical calculations were performed for the acetonitrile molecule on the basis of the KS spectrum determined in the experiment, and the conformation of the molecule was modeled on a computer using the HF/6-31G Hartree-Fock method, and the bond lengths of atoms and the spatial angles between them were determined (Fig. 5). The results obtained using this method can be used in the synthesis of specific targeted chemicals based on the values of the distances and angles between the atoms in the molecules, in the calculation of thermodynamic quantities, and in finding the theoretically calculated values of the polarizability coefficient of the molecules according to the degrees of freedom.

Fig. 6. Bond lengths and angles between atoms in the structure based on quantum-chemical calculations for the acetonitrile molecule

4. CONCLUSION

Based on theoretical calculations and experimental results, the laws of the dependence of the intensities of the spectra on the vibration frequency of the molecule were determined for CS spectrum of light in the frequency range of $0\text{-}3500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and for IR absorption spectra in the range of $4000\text{-}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$. Recommendations were made that the role of C-H bonds in the formation of the CS spectrum is special. Using the CS spectrum of light taken from the experiment, in the substances where H-bonding is observed were determined of this bond's lifetime, energy, time characterizing the vibration frequency of the molecule and the methodology of calculating them theoretically was recommended. In the IR spectrum, it was noted that in addition to C-H bonding, the effects of valence and deformation vibrations are also special. This scientific research work is performed within the framework of the fundamental project, FZ-20200929385 on the topic of "Development of spectroscopic and non-empirical analysis methods for the study and application of nano-sized molecular clusters of biological objects", funded by the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

5. REFERENCES

- [1] . Seleznev B. I., Fedorov D. G. IR – Spectroscopy of silicon dioxide films obtained by low-temperature methods. *Bulletin of the Novgorod State University*, 2017, 5 (103), P. 114-118.
- [2] . Buslov D. K., Sushko N. I., Tretinnikov O. N. Investigation of Hydrogen Bonds in Weakly Hydrated Polyvinyl Alcohol Films by Infrared Spectroscopy. *Polymer science series A*, 2011, 53 (12), P. 1121-1127.
- [3] . Jaswal S. S., Sharma T. P., Wolfram G. Second-order Raman spectra and phonon spectrum of LiD. *Solid State Communications*, 1972, 11 (9), P.1151–1155.
- [4] . Laplaze D. Second-order Raman spectra of LiH. *Physica Status Solidi*, 1979, 91(1), P. 59–69.
- [5] . Anderson A., Lüty F. Raman scattering, defect luminescence, and phonon spectra of ⁷LiH, ⁶LiH, and ⁷LiD crystals. *Phys. Rev.*, 1983, 28 (6), P. 500–503.
- [6] . Katarzyna Z. Gaca-Zajac, Benjamin R. Smith, Alison Nordon, Ashleigh J. Fletcher, Karen Johnston, Jan Sefcik. Investigation of IR and Raman spectra of species present in formaldehyde-water-methanol systems. *J. Vib. Spec.*, 2018, 97, P. 44-54.
- [7] . Eshchanov B., Otajonov Sh., Rakhmatillaeva Kh. Application of Raman scattering of light to study the structure of molecules. *International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, 2018, 9 (5), P. 1532-1534.
- [8] . Eshchanov B., Soliyeva N., Otajonov Sh. Temperature dependence of the parameters of Raman scattering lines in liquids. *Uzbek Journal of Physics*, 2016, 6 (1), P.72-74.
- [9] . Eshchanov B., Otajonov Sh., Isamatov A. On possible models of thermal motion of molecules and temperature effect on relaxation of optical anisotropy in bromine benzene. *Ukr. J. Phys.*, 2011, 56 (11), P. 1178.
- [10] . Eshchanov B., Otajonov Sh., Isamatov A., Bobojonov D. Dynamics of relaxation precesses in liquids: Analysis of oscillation and orientation spectra. *J. Mol. Liq.*, 2015, 202, P. 148-152.
- [11] . Eshchanov B., Otajonov Sh., Mukhamedov G., Dorshenko I., Karpova O., Allakuliyeva Sh. Experimental study of Raman spectra of some aromatic hydrocarbons. *Ukr. J. Phys.*, 2020, 65 (4), P. 284-290.
- [12] . Khabibullaev P. K., Bulavin L. A., Pogorelov V. E., Tukhvatullin F. Kh., Otajonov Sh., Zhumaboev A. Dynamics of molecules in liquids. *Fan*, Tashkent, 2009. 410 p.
- [13] . Gordon A, Ford R. *Companion of the chemist*. Product “Mir”, Moscow, 1976, 439 p.
- [14] . Aston J., Isserow S., Szasz G., Kennedy R. Empirical correlation and method of calculation of barriers hindering internal rotation. *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1944, 12, P. 336-344.
- [15] .Magnasco V. An empirical method for calculating barriers to internal rotation in simple molecules. *Nuovo Cimento*, 1962, 24 (3), P. 425-441.
- [16] . Frenkel Y. I. *Kinetic theory of liquid*. Product AS USSR, Moscow, 1945.